

Research Scenario CLARIAH-VL

Unlocking born-digital literary heritage: The case of the Herman de Coninck floppy disks

Final blogpost on the case of the Herman de Coninck floppy disks

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The aim of the CLARIAH-VL Open Humanities Service Infrastructure is to advance digitally-enabled research in Humanities and the Arts by, among other things, providing data-level access to digitized and born-digital resources. In this blogpost series, we will communicate on research scenarios leading to and building upon the datasets made available through CLARIAH-VL. This is the final blogpost on the research scenario ‘Unlocking born-digital literary heritage: the case of the Herman de Coninck floppy disks’, in which we will focus on the dataset with the file titles related to De Coninck’s columns published under the title “De vliegende keeper” in *De Morgen*.

Aim of the research scenario

In the [previous blogpost](#), we discussed how computational methods could provide some preliminary insights into the contents of the files stored on De Coninck’s floppies. It became clear that many of files on Herman de Coninck’s floppy disks in the archive of the Letterenhuis are related De Coninck’s weekly column ‘De vliegende keeper’ for the Flemish newspaper *De Morgen*, of which a selection also appeared in the collection of essays *De vliegende keeper* (1995). Creating a dataset with the files related to this column would allow for further research, for example, within the field of textual scholarship and genetic criticism. Within genetic criticism, the study of the writing process is usually divided into three levels: the examination of the endogenesis, the exogenesis and the epigenesis. The endogenesis encompasses the actual composition of the text, the exogenesis the incorporation of research into the text, and the epigenesis describes the continuation of the genesis after a text has been published and studies the revisions in later publications. The files on the floppy disks can therefore be well used for epigenetic research, focusing on questions such as: *What can the files on the disks tell us about the publication of this collection? Do the files tell us anything about the selection process? Did the essays need to be rewritten to be republished, or could they simply be published as they were? And what is the status of the digital files on the disks compared to the newspaper version, the version published in the collection of essays, and the versions in the paper archive?*

Method

The steps discussed in the [previous blogpost](#) enabled us to create a dataset with documents that could be linked to the column ‘De vliegende keeper’ on the floppy disks and in De Coninck’s paper archive at the Letterenhuis. We then also compared these files with the essays that were published in the collection of essays *De vliegende keeper*. There were 36 essays republished in *De vliegende keeper*. For only two of these, no digital version seems to have survived in the archive. Yet, there are also four essays of which one or more digital versions exist within the archive, along with a printed version and a version as printed in the newspaper. This is the case for the essay “Poëzie en toeval” (“Poetry and Coincidence”), with one digital floppy disk version, one paper version, one newspaper version and one version as published in the collection of essays. The essay “De kunst van het stamelen” (“The Art of Stammering”) comes in two digital versions along with all the other printed versions, just like “Feestelijke zinloosheid” (“Festive Futility”) and “De avonturen van een spermatozoön” (“The Adventures of a Spermatozoon”). We compared the versions with each other using [Diff Annotator](#). This is a lightweight environment for annotating text comparisons of two plain text files, developed by Vincent Neyt for the eXtant Toolkit for Digital Scholarly Editing, as part of CLARIAH-VL. It produces a visualisation of the variation using the ‘git diff’ command from git (an open source distributed version control system) for the collation process itself. The diff function in git is used to show the changes between commits. The collation results showed that each version of these versions differ slightly from each other.

Handwritten revision of the essay’s title on the printout

Findings

Let’s look more closely at the differences between the versions of the essay “De avonturen van een spermatozoön”, of which the printed version in the paper archive also contains major handwritten revisions. In the essay, De Coninck wrote about the poet Hans Andreus, of whom he had just read a biography written by Jan van der Vegt. Each version represents a unique version of the text – none of the versions are the same. This allows us to draw a hypothesis on the changes that were made to the essay from the first version to the reprint.

DIFF ANNOTATOR

1 DE VLIEGENDE KEEPER

2

3 De fenomenologie van de klootzak
avonturen een spermatozoïde

4 Herman de Coninck

The change in title visualised with Diff Annotator

The first version – within the remaining documents – can be found on one of the floppy disks, called ANDREUS. In this version, the essay is titled “De fenomenologie van een klootzak” (“The Phenomenology of a Scumbag”). This is also the title given to the printed version of the essay. The entire base layer appears to be the same as the first version found on the floppy disks, but it contains unique handwritten revisions: paragraphs are marked for deletion or relocation, sentences are struck through and interlinear and marginal additions appear throughout. One of the revisions addresses the title: it is changed from “De fenomenologie van een klootzak” to “De avonturen van een spermatozoïde” (“The Adventures of a Spermatozoid”). De Coninck implemented the handwritten revisions in the second version found on the floppy disks, but in this process, he included other revisions as well. The digital version is therefore not exactly the same as the paper version with the revisions taken into account. Additionally, there is the version published in the newspaper. This published version most closely resembles the paper version: the handwritten revisions have been considered, but they are not identical. Finally, there is the version published in the collection of essays. This published version bears the closest resemblance to the second version found on the floppy disks, but also contains some differences – mostly minor editorial changes and another title change – a change of spelling of “spermatozoïde” into “spermatozoon”. This indicates that De Coninck did not use the version previously published in the newspaper, but delved into his own archive to find a version to publish in the book.

Final remarks

This very brief overview of the differences between the different versions shows the importance of the digital files in De Coninck’s archive. They are not just digital surrogates for documents in the paper archive, or vice versa, but they are necessary for understanding his working method and the publication process of the “De vliegende keeper” columns.

This research scenario aimed to make the born-digital archival material in Herman de Coninck’s archive at the Letterenhuis findable and more accessible. This led to the creation

and publication of one CSV file with the people and places mentioned in the files and one with all the files related to the “De vliegende keeper”-columns. This was the first exploration of the files, and there is still much to do to fully unlock the born-digital archive. An important question is, for example, how this archive needs to be described. We, therefore, hope we can continue tackling challenges related to born-digital archives in CLARIAH-VL+, in which the Letterenhuis will participate as a third-party partner. In this next phase, we plan to develop a description model for born-digital and hybrid literary archives.

Link to the dataset

The CSV file with the list of documents related to the “De vliegende keeper”-columns is made publicly available on [Zenodo](#) through CLARIAH-VL, the files from the floppies can – after approval – be consulted at the Letterenhuis.

References

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